

iPSC Certificate of Analysis

Product Description	JAX human iPSC line (iNDI panel) containing a genetically engineered mutation	CRISPR-mediated Gene Variant	See product code's specific webpage for details
Parental Cell Line	KOLF2.1J (JAX Product# JIPSC1000) ¹	Gene Editing Strategy	See Product Code's specific webpage for comprehensive design strategy (Sequence Map files)
Cell Type	Induced pluripotent stem cell	Vial Volume	0.5 ml
Species	Homo sapiens	Recovery	See JAX standard protocol
Common Name	Human	Storage:	-196°C (liquid or vapor phase of liquid nitrogen)
Passage Number Range of Distribution LOTS	p4 through p6 ²		

Gene-edited Clone Characterization and Validation³

Test Description	Method	Specification	Result
Gene-edited Variant Sequence Confirmation	PCR and Sanger sequencing of wild type and variant alleles.	Sanger sequence matches predicted design strategy. Heterozygous variants have ~ equal base signal in Sanger traces.	Pass <i>See downloadable Sanger Sequence file in QC data section of cell line webpage.</i>
Karyotype	G-banding with trypsin treatment and Giemsa stain (GTG-banding) of metaphase chromosomes.	> 90% of cells are euploid and exhibit proper G-band pattern.	Pass <i>See downloadable Karyotype file in QC Data section of specific cell line webpage.</i>
Copy Number Variation	Analysis of genomic DNA on Infinium Global Diversity Arrays (GDA) with added NeuroBooster [Ref 1]. ⁴	Genomic integrity of iPS lines, we investigated the B-allele frequency and Log R ratio values of each iPS cell line which were downloaded from Illumina GenomeStudio. Abnormal patterns were observed by visual inspection and were plotted using R (v3.6.1) with the GWASTools package [Ref 2]. Additionally genotyped cell line was compared to the KOLF2.1J WGS data and investigated for large patterns of mismatching SNPs which imply genomic integrity issue and lead to failure to pass.	Pass <i>See downloadable "Array Data" file in QC Data section of specific cell line webpage.</i>

